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The Trust of Merchants in Europe

It decreased on average of 117% for the countries analyzed between February and November 2022.

The Eurostat calculates the value of merchants' trust in Europe. The data is collected monthly and indicates what the traders expect in relation to the trend of retail sales. The indicator is also known as "Retail Confidence Indicator".

Ranking of countries by value of the trust of merchants in November 2022. Slovakia is in the first place for the value of the retail confidential indicator with a value of 24.7 units, followed by Greece with a value of 20.4 units and Turkey with a value of 19.3. In the middle of the standings there are Poland with a value equal to -1.1 units, followed by Croatia with a value equal to -1.3 units and by France with a value equal to -3.3 units. Hungary closes the ranking with a value equal to -18.2 units, followed by Germany with a value equal to -26 units and by Denmark with a value equal to -35.8 units. On average in the period considered the value of merchants' trust has decreased by a value equal to -1.08%.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage variation of the trust of traders between February 2022 and November 2022. Italy is in the first place due to percentage variation of consumers' trust between February 2022 and November 2022 with a value of +171.43% equal to an amount of 10.8 units, followed by the Netherlands with a value of a value of 113.33% equal to an amount of 3.4 units and Greece with a variation of 78.95% even to an amount of 9 units. In the middle of the standings there are Albania with a value equal to -30.59% equal to an amount of -2.6 units, followed by France with a value equal to -57.14% equal to an amount of -1, 2 units and Montenegro with a variation of -78.26% equal to an amount of -7.2 units. Finland closes the ranking with a value equal to -2.371.43% equal to an amount of -16.6 units, followed by Germany with a value of 2,700.00% equal to an amount of -27 units and by Denmark with A value of -9.050.00% equal to an amount of -36.2 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. The results highlight the presence of two Clusters as indicated below or:

- Cluster 1: Cyprus, Hungary, France, Austria, Germany, North Macedonia, Finland, Belgium, Denmark, Poland, Lithuania, Spain, Ireland, Greece, Netherlands, Portugal, Latvia;
- Cluster 2: Bulgaria, Turkey, Czech Republic, Slovenia, Slovakia, Montenegro, Serbia, Estonia, Italy, Albania, Romania, Sweden, Croatia, Malta.

From the median point of view, it appears that the value of the 2-C2 cluster is equal to an amount of 7.4 units, while the value of the 1-C1 cluster is equal to an amount of -5.7 units. It therefore follows that $C2 = 7.4 > C1 = -5.7$. From a geographical point of view except for Sweden and Estonia, almost all countries that have a growth in the value of merchants' trust are countries of southern and Eastern Europe or countries with medium-low pro-beam income. One of the motivations that could justify

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this phenomenon derives from the fact that in the countries that have medium-low per capita income, consumption tend to always be high, since generally people who have medium-low incomes acquire necessary primary goods, or food, home, clothing. On the contrary, in the countries where pro-capita income is medium-high consumption is not consisting only of primary consumption as even from consumption of status or social consumption that serve to manifest belonging to a certain social class rather than to satisfy needs essentials of the population.

Network analysis with Manhattan distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with Manhattan distance. Three structures with complex networks and four structures with simplified networks are identified.

There is a network structure as indicated below or:

- Bulgaria has a connection with the Czech Republic equal to an amount of 0.65 units, and with Turkey for a value of 0.94 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Turkey for a value of 0.8 units and with Bulgaria for a value of 0.65 units;
- Turkey has a connection with Bulgaria for a value of 0.94 units, with the Czech Republic for a value of 0.8 units and with Slovakia for a value of 0.92 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Turkey for a value of 0.92 units and with Slovenia for a value of 0.83 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with a value of 0.83 units.

There is a complex network structure as indicated below or:

- The Netherlands have a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.47 units;
- Portugal has a connection with Spain for a value equal to 0.93 units, with the Netherlands for a value of 0.47 units and with Latvia for a value of 0.8 units;
- Latvia has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.8 units and with Croatia for a value of 0.69 units;
- Croatia has a connection with Latvia for a value of 0.69 units.

There is a complex network structure between the following countries:

- Lithuania has a connection with Poland for a value of 0.57 units;
- Poland has a connection with Lithuania for a value of 0.57 units and with North Macedonia for a value of 0.93 units;
- Northern Macedonia has a connection with Poland for a value of 0.93 units.

There are also four structures with simplified networks as indicated below or:

- Cyprus and France are connected for a value of 0.57 units;
- Montenegro and Serbia are connected for a value of 0.68 units;
- Austria and Finland are connected for a value of 0.93 units;
- Germany and Denmark are connected for a value of 0.86 units.

Network analysis is used to identify propagation effects between the various countries that are analyzed. For example, if the merchants' trusted index increases in Portugal, then this should cause an increase even in the Netherlands, Spain, and Latvia. Obviously, this report also works in the event of the reduction of the merchants' trusted index. It is thus possible to identify maps to predict how the phenomena of distrust or trust of consumers will be spread.

Conclusions. The merchants' trusted index has significantly decreased between February and November 2022. If you take the average value, it is possible to note that this value has decreased from an amount of 6.3 up to a value of -1.08 or an equal variation at -7.4 units equal to -117.056%. There are countries where this indicator has grown as for example Italy, the Netherlands and Greece. However, in most countries the merchants' trusted index has decreased, and this reduction has also been significant in countries such as Germany and other medium-high income countries. This indicator could indicate a negative forecast for the trend of consumption in Europe. And since consumption constitutes a significant part of GDP, or about 70-80% according to countries, this value could be the clear signal of an incipient recession.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

